

Seeing the forest through the trees: A systematic review approach to the compilation of relevant and useful tools and learning materials in support of multi-actor project developmentAuthor names: Evelien Cronin^a, Hanne Cooreman^a and Elke Rogge^aAffiliation: ^aILVO – Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

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Short abstract (200 words):

The Multi-Actor (MA) approach under the Horizon Europe (HE) programme has been posited as a promising instrument to better connect research and innovation projects to practice in agriculture, forestry and rural development sectors. However, bringing together different societal actors with complementary knowledge and skills in European projects is challenging. As part of the PREMIERE project, a MA HE project, we aim to build a database of tools and learning materials to support the first phase of multi-actor HE projects, i.e. the co-creative proposal-writing, consortium building, drafting of a MA strategy and the setting up of the project management approach. We explain how to build such a database of tools by combining a rigorous scientific methodology to implement a desktop mapping of tools, i.e., ‘Systematic Review’, with an iterative, user-focused and multi-actor approach. This combination is essential as this phase of MA projects has its own distinct characteristics and needs. A profound insight into which tools and learning materials are available combined with how time-consuming, complex or resource intensive they are is thus fundamental. Elaborating possible tools to include harder to reach actors can be an empowering exercise and a game-changer in terms of the inclusivity and potential of MA projects.

1. Purpose

The PREMIERE project aims to support prospective Horizon Europe project consortia which are expected to apply the Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) during proposal writing, project work and beyond. While the MAA is posited as a promising instrument to ‘speed up innovation’, in practice, making best use of complementary knowledge from different types of actors is challenging and not always straightforward. Within PREMIERE, the aim is to provide learning material and tools, and offer training and networking events for actors, policy makers and executive agencies especially to support the proposal-writing phase of multi-actor (MA) Horizon Europe projects. A part of this work consists of the compilation of a database of already available tools (such as co-innovation methodologies, webinars, guidelines, videos and toolkits) which can provide support in drafting and implementing a MA strategy, building a MA project consortium, the co-creative writing process and the management of a MA project.

Databases of tools or the development of toolkits are a popular and rather well-known characteristic and output of many MA Horizon Europe or Horizon 2020 projects, see for example, the FarmDemo training kit¹ or the SHERPA Stakeholder Engagement tools². Yet, the process behind the compilation of these toolkits, guidelines, or databases often remains a black box. In this abstract, we aim to shed light on how to iteratively build a database of tools which combines a rigorous scientific methodology to implement a desktop mapping of tools, i.e., Systematic Review (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2020), with an iterative, user-focused and multi-actor approach (EIP-AGRI, 2017). The latter implies a continuous

¹ <https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/>

² <https://rural-interfaces.eu/resources-and-tools/stakeholder-engagement-tools/>

checking and consulting with the intended users of the database on their needs, current level of knowledge on and awareness of already available tools.

The fundamental reason underpinning the use of such a rigorous approach to the set-up of the PREMIERE tool database, is its specific scope. While in other examples of these toolboxes, the focus is to support actors or processes in a stage where they have secured funding. In contrast, the PREMIERE tool database aims to bring together tools which can support a multi-actor process starting in the phase where there is no funding available yet. Neither is there the certainty at that point in time that the funding for their work will be acquired, while the time and other resources needed to compile a project proposal is typically perceived as scarce. This phase of MA projects thus has its own distinct characteristics and needs in terms of support (Cronin et al., 2022). Mostly because research shows that especially under time pressure, people tend to revert to established routines, rely on shortcuts and quick fixes to solve complex problems instead of discussing and debating them (Cronin et al., 2022; Fieldsend et al., 2020; Verouden et al., 2016). This also entails that new potential proposal writing partners who are unfamiliar with the rules and routines have a disadvantage. This toolkit has the ambition to respond to the needs of these partners as well. The tools which we aim to collect and compile can thus not be too time-consuming, complex or require any large amount of resources to implement. In conclusion, using and searching this envisaged toolbox should be a straightforward and quick activity.

2. Approach and methodology

In order to ensure a rigorous and scientific approach to compile the PREMIERE database, we have developed a methodology that combines a systematic review approach (1) to map existing learning materials and tools, with a user-consulted approach (2). The systematic review approach is often referred to by authors implementing literature reviews in educational research (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2020). The logic behind this approach is that in order to review the existing information available on a particular topic, one needs an explicit, accountable and rigorous research method. Our research question does not comprise a collation of the scientific knowledge available on a specific topic, but rather a compilation of learning materials and tools available to and potentially useful and relevant for participants in MA project consortia. Therefore, we have adapted the linear nine step process described in Zawacki-Richter et al. (2020). We translated it into an iterative process where desktop research is complemented with user interactions. This combination should help assure that in the process of database compilation not only a complete scanning, with clearly defined boundaries, of currently available tools and learning materials is done but also that the final database includes those tools and learning materials useful and relevant to the targeted group of users. The overall process is illustrated in Figure 1 below and each step will be further specified in the following section.

Figure 1. Systematic Review approach to database compilation with user interactions (adapted from Zawacki-Richter et al., 2020)

3. Setting up the systematic review approach

As an extension to the systematic review approach, we aim to complement the desktop search for learning materials and tools with user interactions in three distinct ways (indicated with a 'person' icon in the figure); a) an online survey with 'users' on what types of tools and learning materials they would envision (selection criteria) and b) this survey will also ask which tools they have used before (develop search strategy) and c) workshops to test and validate the quality, relevance and usefulness of the tools which passed the coding and characterising step of the systematic review process. In this extended abstract, we detail our approach related to each step of a systematic review approach as depicted in Figure 1. We have divided the steps of the systematic review approach into two distinct phases. In the boundary-setting phase, the iterative process aims at setting the key boundaries to the database compilation in order to ensure an effective search. In the consolidation phase, the process aims at consolidating the final database by introducing a structure to the tools and compiling them. Each of these phases include several steps which we will explain in the following paragraphs.

Phase 1 – Boundary setting

First, **the research question and user groups** need to be clearly defined. In our case, the research question consists of two parts: 1) Which tools and learning materials are currently available in support of actors engaged in MA project proposals and co-creative proposal-writing, and 2) Which tools and learning materials are useful for and relevant to actors engaged in MA project proposals and co-creative proposal-writing?

Second, **the conceptual framework** (CF) clarifying the main assumptions of the search is elaborated. This provides a baseline upon which certain types of tools or learning materials are in- and excluded. Our focus is to support the development of MA Horizon Europe projects and a better inclusion of the needed variety of relevant societal actors in a balanced way during the project preparation phase. Consequently, our conceptual framework entails on the one hand an elaboration of clusters of activities related to MA project preparation and on the other hand the development of the type of actors involved in the form of 'user personas' (Table 1). The three clusters of activities we define as a) those related to networking and consortium building, b) writing and the development of the project approach and c) the management of administrative and technical requirements.

Table 1. MA project user personas (based upon Cronin et al., 2022; Fieldsend et al., 2020, 2021)

User persona	Description
Project leaders	Actors who have been involved in multiple European projects, especially under the RI funding framework. Either they have been the coordinator of such projects before, or they aspire to coordinate these types of projects in the future.
Project followers	Actors who have been involved in a few European projects, especially under the RI funding framework. They know how these projects work, but do not have the ambition to play a large or leading role in these projects. They are often task or sometimes WP leaders.
Novices	Under the novices, we see two types : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-initiators: These are actors who have never been involved in these types of projects, but are interested in participation. They take initiative to be involved and would like to be more involved in the future. - Invitees: These actors have been invited by other actors to be involved in this type of European project, but would not have taken any initiative themselves. They are not interested in being more involved in the future at first sight.

Third, in the **construction of selection criteria** there is the combination of the desktop mapping and user interaction. The selection criteria will be a combination of practical (e.g., available in English, free access), theoretical (e.g., evidence-based) and user specific (e.g., quick to understand) considerations. This step involves a user-interaction to get first insights into which types of characteristics tools and learning materials should have according to users. These will be collected using an online survey with users who have been involved in MA project proposals before.

The **search strategy** builds on the selection criteria and the user input. We aim to apply a snowball sampling strategy (Parker et al., 2019). As many other MA projects have compiled tools or learning materials in support of multi-actor processes, we first explore the list of MA projects available on the EIP AGRI Service Point website³. Using the reference lists of these lists of tools and toolboxes, we explore other tools, toolkits and learning materials. The themes specified under the conceptual framework are used as Google search terms. Also, the user survey will provide inputs on the direction of our search and what users consider to be relevant sources. We do not aspire to be exhaustive, rather we aim to enable the identification of relevant, useful and user-friendly tools, toolkits and learning materials in line with our research question.

This brings us to the last step of this phase, **the selection of tools, toolkits and learning materials**. At this point, the tools and other learning materials identified under the search undergo a checking or screening process. As indicated in Figure 1, in this screening process, we might want to revisit and further fine-tune or specify the research questions and the subsequent step. We aim to implement this step in two stages: in a first stage, we evaluate the relevance of the scope of the tools or learning materials at first sight (language, checking of key terms such as ‘multi-actor’, ‘participatory’) to see their likely relevance, after which a more in-depth review is done against the scope of the themes and user personas described in the CF. This selection and reviewing step is planned to be done using researcher triangulation, to strengthen the validity.

Phase 2 – Consolidation

The second phase starts by **“coding” and “characterising” the tools and learning materials**. This process includes a) for who these tools or learning materials would be interesting (cfr. the user personas), b) how they will support the MA project development, c) when and to which end can they be supportive in the MA project development and d) any other characteristics which would be relevant

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/about/multi-actor-projects-scientists-and-farmers>

based upon the insights from the user surveys. This step will feed back into the selection, as it might indicate that some search paths remained underexplored.

Next, the **quality assessment and user validation** will be implemented. At this point, we double-check the quality and usability of the tools and learning materials. On the one hand, this can be done based upon a review of the original source and the clarity of the description of the tools and materials. On the other hand, the selected and coded tools and learning materials will undergo a testing and validation exercise with users. We will organise workshops bringing together different user personas to check the fit of the tools and learning materials with their own expectations and needs.

In the final steps, the **database is compiled** into a user-friendly online repository. Furthermore, using the insights gained, we will **report on whether in the wide array of tools, toolkits and learning materials available there are any blind spots and gaps** when it comes to supporting actors in their involvement in MA project proposal writing.

4. Practical Implications

While the 'multi-actor approach' increasingly gains attention and importance when it comes to acquiring funding under the Horizon Europe programme, the reality is that this type of approach not only requires quite some efforts in terms of time and resources, but also specific types of skills and capacities from engaged actors. In order for these projects to become more inclusive to a wide range of societal actors, such as advisors, teachers, facilitators or even farmers, there is a need to provide easy and low barrier access to tools and learning materials that fit the needs of these different types of actors. Compiling a database which explicitly considers not only the needs of organisations or actors usually involved in and highly motivated to be part of these MA projects, but also those of harder to reach groups, or groups of actors with a limited amount of time and resources available or a low or no up-front intrinsic motivation to become part of these large consortia can be empowering for different types of potential actors, and finally a game-changer.

5. Theoretical Implications

The scientific and theoretical value of this abstract and our approach to the database compilation is twofold:

- 1) It applies the well-known methodological framework of Systematic Reviews to a new topic, i.e. the compilation of a database of tools and learning materials instead of a literature review.
- 2) The findings of the iterative cycles and the user interactions, will provide deeper insights into how transdisciplinary research and innovation projects, such as the MA Horizon Europe projects in the agriculture, forestry and rural development sector, gain form and what the different needs in terms of information, skills and communication are from different types of actors.

6. References

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